

Potential Medicinal Plants for treatment of Diabetes in Sonbhadra District , Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract

Medicinal plants have potential for treating various ailments due to presence of secondary metabolites. Diabetes is becoming very common disease which is serious metabolic disorder nowadays and large number of medicines are available for treatment. Drugs available also impart some side affects, are expensive and also come with several complications. Aborigines, villagers or the natives of the forest are not well connected to modern day medicine and are dependent on the surrounding flora of Sonbhadra district for livelihood, medicines. The ethnomedicines are found to be easily available as compared to modern day medicines which are costly and out of reach by many of inhabitants. The present study was undertaken for documentation of potential plants used for treatment of diabetes. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic endocrine disorder which occurs due to high blood glucose levels interfering with carbohydrate, protein, and fat metabolism is caused due to the deficiency in production of insulin released by pancreas. The present paper reveals ethnomedicinal information of 10 plants from ... families by tribal communities of Sonbhadra District which are found promising and effective for treatment of diabetes.

Keywords Secondary Metabolites, Diabetes Mellitus, Ethnomedicinal Information.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is an endocrine disorder caused due to high blood glucose levels affecting carbohydrate, protein, and fat metabolism (Bastaki 2005). β -Langerhans of pancreas are not able to produce sufficient insulin due to which the peripheral tissues are deficient in its uptake (Al-Goblan *et al.* 2014). The function of insulin hormone is to regulate sugar in blood and it stimulates liver to metabolize glucose by stimulating cells of fat and muscles in drop of blood sugar level to normal level. If a person is diabetic, the blood sugar level remains high due to nil or ineffective production of insulin by the pancreas (Dean and McEntyre 2004). It is caused due to the deficit production of insulin by the β -Langerhans islet cells of the pancreas or due to defective insulin uptake in the peripheral tissues (Al-Goblan *et al.* 2014). An increase in the blood glucose level immediately after a meal triggers the release of insulin hormone from the pancreas. Insulin stimulates the liver to metabolize glucose and also stimulates the fat and muscle cells to remove glucose from the blood which results in a drop of blood sugar level to normal levels. If a person is diabetic, the blood sugar level remains high due to nil or ineffective production of insulin by the pancreas (Dean and McEntyre 2004).

Objective of study

The present paper reveals about 10 plants along with ethnomedicinal importance in treatment for Diabetes mellitus.

Review of Literature

Medicinal plants along with ethnobotanical research has gained importance since it is quite helpful in discovery of plant based drugs. It has been also reported that modern day drugs are developed from natural plant products (Suresh Kumar *et al.*, 2021). It has also been noticed that plant based drugs are easily available have

simple application and are economical (Rahman *et al.* 2019; Jadeja *et al.*, 2006). Sonbhadra district is also considered to be the largest district of Uttar Pradesh. It inhabits rich flora of medicinal plants among which many plants are used for treatment of diabetes mellitus. During the exploration on tribals valuable information were gathered which has been mentioned in this paper. The Sonbhadra district occupies southernmost part of Uttar Pradesh which is surrounded in north by Mirzapur and Varanasi district of U.P, and in south by Surguja district of Chattisgarh and in south east by Palamu district of Jharkhand (Singh and Singh, 1992). A extensive ethnobotanical survey has also been conducted previously by many taxonomists, ethnobotanist and environmentalist till date (Bhattacharya, 1963, 1964; Maheshwari and Singh, 1986; Jain, 1991; Singh *et al.* 2002; Narain and Singh, 2006; Narain *et al.*, 2005, 2006; Singh *et al.* 2010; Singh and Narain, 2010; Lata and Singh, 2015; Singh, 2017, Singh, 2024).

Diabetes is a serious metabolic disorder that affects many other metabolic functions of body and several marketed medications are available to alleviate the symptoms of diabetes. Plants having the medicinal value for treating Diabetes have been reported to have significant anti-diabetic properties. They also have been reported to have anti diabetic compounds as flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolics and tannins which have been reported for improving the efficacy of cells of pancreas to enhance the secretion of insulin (Kooti *et al.* 2016). According to the survey of literature it has been reported that there are almost 410 medicinal plants proven to have anti-diabetic properties but 109 plants have been studied intensely with complete mechanism all over the world (Prabhakar and Doble 2008).

Sampling

The ethnobotanical survey was conducted during various seasons from 2019 to 2023 by the author who collected almost 50 plants showing ethnomedicinal importance regarding Diabetes mellitus. Out of 50 plants collected 10 plants have been identified for having potential for curing the ailment have been identified with the help of various published worldwide flora (Hooker, 1872-1897; Duthie, 1903-1929; Verma *et al.* 1994; Mudgal *et al.* 1997; Singh *et al.*, 2001; Srivastava, 1995). The identity of these species are confirmed by comparing with authentically identified specimens of herbarium of Botanical Survey of India, Central Circle, Allahabad and Duthie Herbarium, Department of Botany, University of Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh. Correct nomenclature of each species with citation, description of the plant and ethnomedicinal documentation has been provided in this research paper.

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Result and Discussion

Structured questionnaire survey method was employed and documentation of traditional ethnomedicinal practice of tribal communities for rheumatism has been recorded. The uses of plants for diabetes mellitus has been given in the tabular form.

S No.	Botanical name	Family	Common name	Part used	Application
1.	Amle marmelos (L.) Correa	Rutaceae	Basel	Fruit	250mg of fruit is given twice a day.
2.	Coriandrum sativum L.	Apiaceae	Dhaniya	Leaves and stolon	Crushed leaves with stolon given 2 times a day.
3.	Syzygium cumini (L.) Skeels	Myrtaceae	Jamun	Seeds	Powdered seeds are given after every meal.
4.	Gymnema sylvestre (Retz.) R.Br.ex Sm.	Apocyanaceae	Gurmar	Entire plant	Decoction of entire plant given 2 times a day.
5.	Momordica charantia L.	Cucurbitaceae	Karela	Fruit	Fresh juice given after every meal.
6.	Oscimum sanctum L.	Lamiaceae	Tulsi	Leaves	Decoction of leaves are given after every meal.
7.	Phyllanthus emblica L.	Euphorbiaceae	Amla	Fruit	Juice of fruit given empty stomach
8.	Allium sativum L.	Alliaceae	Lahsun	Bulb	2-3 cloves given empty stomach with warm water.
9.	Aloe vera (L.) Burm.f.	Asphodelaceae	Ghrirkumari	Entire plant	Pulp is given with juice of Phyllanthus emblica L.
10.	Curcuma longa L.	Zingiberaceae	Halci	Rhizome	Crushed part of rhizome is given empty stomach.

Conclusion

: Ethnobotanical exploration and research is gaining tremendous value all over the world because it is opening avenue for discovery of potent and cost effective drugs. The present exploration mentions 10 common plants available in abundance in Sonbhadra district belonging to 10 families for treating diabetes mellitus. Plant diversity is rich in Sonbhadra. Treating diabetes from commonly available plants from traditional knowledge documentation has become area of interest as the treatment is quite cost effective. As mentioned earlier Sonbhadra district is one of the largest district of Uttar Pradesh and many parts of this is still unexplored, the area needs special attention for exploration and documentation of ethnomedicinal importance so that it attracts various researchers from pharmacological field to further developing new drugs against the illness.

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